

Research

Internally Displaced Persons in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Case Study of Malkohi Camp Nigeria (2009-2014)

Sambo Augustine Miriam

College of Liberal Arts Shanghai University, China

Abstract: This paper analyses Nigerian government interventions and policies to protect the human security of IDPs. These policies include providing IDPs with shelter, food, and nutritional assistance; access to clean water and health care; education for children who are victims of humanitarian crises; and protection for these vulnerable groups. It draws upon human security theory (HST) to assess the needs and challenges confronting IDPs in sub-Saharan Africa, it employs a case study approach, with a focus on the Malkohi (IDP) camp in Adamawa State, Nigeria, in the period 2009 to 2014. The paper concludes with findings on the challenges faced by IDPs in adjusting to life in the camp, which include coping with issues related to food, housing, health, safety, and other necessities. These were found to be the most significant challenges faced by IDPs. This paper examined how effective government policies have been able to meet the needs of IDPs, particularly the needs of women and children. The paper concludes that IDPs particularly women and children faced challenges adjusting to life in the camp. Secondly, the policy responses of the Nigerian government do not offer adequate solutions to the challenges faced by IDPs, especially for women and children.

Keywords: Children, Human Security Theory, Internally Displaced Persons, Nigeria, and Women

*Corresponding Author

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Introduction

"Internal displacement was placed on the international agenda and recognized as an important issue of global concern in the early 1990s," according to the Internal Displacement Monitoring Center (IDMC).¹ The number of IDPs in Nigeria has significantly increased because of natural disasters, conflicts between different religions, fights between

¹ Sabella O. Abidde. *The Challenges of Refugees and Internally Displaced Persons in Africa*. Switzerland Springer: (2021) p.3

different groups of people, and the Boko Haram insurgency in the Northeast and some parts of the Northwest.² Displaced persons “are persons or groups of people who have been forced or obligated to flee or to have cause to leave their homes or place of habitual residence in particular, as a result of or to avoid the effect of armed conflict, situations of generalized violence, violations of human rights, or natural or human-made disasters, and they must either remain within their national borders (as IDPs) or have crossed an internationally recognized state border (as refugees).”³ The total number of IDPs in Nigeria as of February 28, 2023, stands at 3,120,206.⁴ Since 2009, the northeastern part of Nigeria, which is made up of six states (Borno, Adamawa, Yobe, Bauchi, and Taraba), has experienced significant population displacement, generating major socio-economic challenges.⁵ IDPs in Nigeria have also had trouble with not getting enough care, not being able to do things on their own, not having enough finance, their families breaking up, and not getting a good education.⁶ The ongoing security crisis in the Northeast caused by the escalation of violence from the Boko Haram insurgency resulted in a greater number of IDPs, posing significant risks to their human security. Thus, human security is, “(defined as freedom from want, fear, and indignities as universal and indivisible components).”⁷

Internal displacement in Nigeria is marked by more and more conflict between people in recent times the insurgency (Boko Haram) crisis in the northeast, which increased the number of IDPs in Nigeria. Certainly, the key to addressing the challenges of IDPs is addressing the causes of displacement, although, addressing the causes also extends to meeting IDPs’ needs. But, to address the challenges faced by IDPs one needs to address the causes of displacement. Empirical research has shown that people’s susceptibility to internal displacement in Nigeria is not only due to natural and human-made disasters, armed conflicts, and ethnic-religious political conflicts, but is also worsened by extreme poverty, a lack of equal access to socio-economic resources, unbalanced development, the high unemployment rate among able-bodied and unsatisfied youths, as well as development and environmental-induced displacement.⁸ These are some of the causes of internal displacement in Nigeria, which has increased the number of IDPs.

This paper critically examines how effective Nigerian government policies are in meeting the needs of IDPs, particularly the needs of women and children. A case study methodology is used to study the Malkohi (IDP) camp in Nigeria’s Adamawa state. A study of the Malkohi camp was conducted to examine how important the IDPs’ situation

² F. Funmi. Coping with Challenges of the Internally Displaced Person Feature Slider [Retrieved from <http://dailyindependentnigeria.com/2014/07/coping-with-challenges-of-internally-displaced-persons-features-slider/>] (2014) [Accessed on October 12, 2022]

³ M. T. Ladan. *Migration, Trafficking, Human Rights, and Refugees under International Law: A Case Study of Africa Nigeria*: Ahmadu Bello University Press. (2006)

⁴ UNCHR. Nigeria Situation. Retrieved from Situation Nigeria Situation (UNHCR.org) (2023) [Accessed March 18, 2023].

⁵ Ruth Mba. IDPs and the Need for Reinterpretation (Retrieved from [https://www.medium.com/@ruthmba/the- plight-of-internally-displaced-persons-idps-and-the-need-for-reinterration-B7555c212f37\(2017\)](https://www.medium.com/@ruthmba/the- plight-of-internally-displaced-persons-idps-and-the-need-for-reinterration-B7555c212f37(2017))) [As of November 15, 2021]

⁶ Faith Osasumwen Olanrewaju, Femi Omotoso, and Joshua Olaniyi Alabi. Datasets on the challenges of forced displacement and coping strategies among displaced women in selected IDP camps in Nigeria 【Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6091441/>】 (2018). [As of October 27, 2021]

⁷ Shahrbanou Tadjbakhsh. *Routledge Handbook of Human Security: In Defense of the Broad View of Human Security*. (2013). p. 43 [As of November 22, 2021]

⁸ National policy on internally displaced persons (IDPs) in Nigeria, Federal Republic of Nigeria, August 2012: p.11

is and how effective the Nigerian government is in responding to their needs, particularly the needs of women and children. Equally, a study of the Malkohi camp was conducted to better understand the needs of women and children.

The next section presents the research design and a review of the current academic literature on the causes of this displacement, the challenges IDPs present for the Nigerian government, the policies and programs put in place to address the needs of IDPs and their effectiveness, particularly for women and children. The next section goes into more detail about the case study of the Malkohi camp, focusing on how well government policies meet the needs of IDPs, particularly the needs of women and children who have been displaced. The final section sums up the main conclusions by examining the challenges faced by IDPs in adjusting to life in the Malkohi camp, which include coping with issues related to food, housing, health, safety, and other necessities. The paper examined how effective government policies have been able to meet the needs of IDPs, particularly the needs of women and children.

Research Methodology

To better understand the needs of displaced women and children, a study of the Malkohi camp was undertaken. This research was carried out during February and March of 2022. It investigated the experiences of IDPs through semi-structured interviews, thirty respondents were chosen from among the 208 families with IDPs in the research area (Malkohi camp). The interviewees were chosen based on their ability to respond to interviews. The interview cohort included both males and females, as well as children; however, women outnumbered men because the study focuses on women and children. For interviews, nine men (9), three children (3), and eighteen (18) displaced women (20 and older) were selected as a result, 60% of those interviewed were women, 30% were males, and 10% were children. Interviewees included men and women of different statuses, such as single, married, widowed, or elderly with interview sessions (40 minutes) conducted on an individual basis. In addition, two National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) officers were interrogated; the official percentage was 6.25 percent.

Literature Review

This section will examine the literature on the causes of displacement, the challenges IDPs present for the Nigerian government, and the policies and programs put in place to address the needs of IDPs, particularly the needs of women and children. Several studies reveal the causes of displacement. For example, Dan⁹ identified the causes of displacement issues affecting IDPs and the reasons why they are so common in Africa. Adamu and Rasheed¹⁰ investigated the prevalence of some major causes of displacement such as insecurity in northern Nigeria. Hence, they emphasize the difficulties that IDPs face in Nigeria.

Azam¹¹ examined IDPs' needs during and after displacement to be associated with overcrowded housing, poverty, economic deprivation, and lack of access to basic needs like water, food, and a safe environment. Akuto et al¹² studied the health challenges encountered by IDPs such as sexually transmitted diseases like syphilis, and HIV/AIDS

⁹ Dan Kuwali. From Durable Solutions to Holistic Solutions: Displacement Prevention in Africa. *African Journal of Legal Studies* 6, South Africa: Martinus Nijhoff Publishers: (2013): p. 265-285

¹⁰ A. Adamu and Z.H Rasheed. Prognosis and Diagnosis of the Effects of Insecurity on Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Northern Nigeria." *Global Journal of Human-Social Science: Political Science*, 16(1), 2016: 10–21

¹¹ J.P. Azam. *Betting on Displacement: Oil, Violence, and the Switch to Civilian Rule in Nigeria*. Brookings Institution (2005). The University of Bern Project on International Displacement: Addressing Internal Displacement: A Framework for National Responsibility. (2009)

¹² G.W Akuto. Challenges of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Nigeria: Implications for Counselling and the Role of Key Stakeholders. 5(2) (2017): p. 21–27. [Retrieved from <http://seahipaj.org/journals/ci/june2017/IJIPSD/full/IJIPSD-J-4-2017.pdf>]

as a result of unprotected sex. Rubia et al¹³ investigated health-related issues that might arise from researching the true nature of the displacement and the IDPs' predicament of IDPs' needs. Dominic¹⁴ emphasized the management of IDPs and the role of humanitarian, non-governmental, and government organizations. Shittu Raji, Folashade Arinola Adekayaoja.¹⁵ studied the situation of IDPs, the coping mechanism, and NEMA's responses to their needs. Furthermore, studies on the management and responses of the Nigerian government to the IDP situation had also been carried out across the country. Augustine¹⁶ investigated the Nigerian government and institutions for the management of displaced people. The evidence he reviewed shows key criteria for the availability of aid and assistance from the government to ensure the human security of IDPs. Louisa¹⁷ examined how the Nigerian government protects IDPs and their legal rights. Therefore, this paper examined the challenges faced by IDPs in adjusting to life in the camp, which include coping with issues related to food, housing, health, safety, and other necessities. It equally examined how effective government policies have been able to meet the needs of IDPs, particularly the needs of women and children.

Nevertheless, the Nigerian government in its effort to address the challenges of IDPs, especially for women and children, some records emerged in the recent time. National Commission for Refugees, Migrants, and Internally Displaced Persons¹⁸ explore the provisions made by the government to assist IDPs. Despite these, efforts the research concluded that government does not offer adequate solutions to the challenges faced by IDPs, especially for women and children. For example, the Nigerian government has developed strategies to address the needs of IDPs.

Theoretical Framework: Human Security Theory

This paper critically analyses Nigerian government interventions and policies to protect the human security of IDPs. Human Security has been defined by CHS in its final report:

"To protect the vital core of all human lives in ways that enhance human freedoms and human fulfillment. "Human security means protecting fundamental freedoms—the freedoms that are the essence of life." It means protecting people from critical (severe) and pervasive (widespread) threats and situations. It means using processes

¹³ M. Rubia, Marcos I, Muening P.A. Increased risk of heart disease among foreign-born females residing in the United States *American Journal of Preventive Medicine* (2002) 222:30-5

¹⁴ Dominic Shimawua. Appraisal of the Management of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Nigeria *International Journal of Knowledge and Dynamic Systems*, volume 14, number 2: (2020): p. 65–70

¹⁵ Shittu Raji, Folashade Arinola Adekayaojas, et al. North-Eastern Nigeria: Assessing the National Emergency Management Agency's Response Capacity to the Plights of Internally Displaced Persons [Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/352277395_Northeastern_Nigeria_assessing_the_response_capacity_of_the_National_Emergency_Management_Agency_to_the_plights_of_internally_displaced_persons]. (2021): p. 2–3. [Accessed November 11, 2021]

¹⁶ Augustine Nduka Eneanya *Handbook of Research on Environmental Policies for Emergency Management and Public Safety USA*: IGI Global, (2018): p. 110

¹⁷ Louisa N. Amaechi. *Human Security of Internationally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Terror-Counterterrorism and Communal Conflicts in Northcentral Nigeria*. Owerri: Federal University of Technology: (2019): p.24

¹⁸ National Commission for Refugees, Migrants, and Internally Displaced Persons, 2017 Budget Defense. At the House Committee on Internally Displaced Persons, Refugees, and Initiatives in the Northeast Zone, held on Wednesday, February 15, 2017, in meeting room 327, the House of Representatives, the National Assembly, and the Three Arms Zone in Abuja, (2017)

that build on people's strengths and aspirations. It means creating a political, social, economic, military, and cultural system that together gives people the building blocks of survival, livelihood, and dignity."¹⁹

People are at the heart of human security, which means that it emphasizes individuals' day-to-day lives, their overall well-being, and their potential to live a life that is both free and healthy.²⁰ Thus providing the background for the stipulation of sovereignty as a responsibility under the watchful eye of the international bodies to hold national governments accountable and offer them a helping hand in ensuring the physical, psychological, moral, and material well-being of all those under their jurisdiction.²¹ The conceptual framework of HST has contributed to the establishment of guidelines for the investigation of IDP needs. This conceptual framework provides policy guidelines for conceptualizing and devising strategies for preventing displacement, providing protection and aid during relocation, and seeking long-term solutions.²² This policy guideline has been especially helpful for the Nigerian government which has resorted to a policy of camp settlement to protect IDPs from the pervasive threats that affect their survival, livelihood, and dignity, all of which are seriously threatened. This is done regarding the effective management of the situation. It ensures the provision of relief supplies for the fulfillment of basic material needs as well as the mobilization of assistance from various organizations.²³

Case Study of Malkohi IDP Camp: The Experiences of Women and Children

Millions of people have been displaced within Nigeria due to natural disasters, religious and, armed conflicts, as well as ethnic conflicts. Over 2 million people are still displaced as a result of the insurgency issue in the Northeast, which comes after a decade of hostilities and crises brought on by the Boko Haram terrorist groups.²⁴ This paper focuses on assessing the effectiveness of Nigerian government policies in addressing the needs of IDPs, especially the needs of women and children in Northern Nigeria who lives in camps.²⁵ The Malkohi camp settlement was established in March 2015 in Yola North, a local government district in Adamawa State, to house people displaced from the states in the northeast. Malkohi village's primary school serves as temporary housing for the displaced people (IDP camp). It is organized into various households.

The IDPs are housed in a makeshift leather house, with a water tank, and a pit latrine. Classes for IDP children occasionally took place in dilapidated classrooms. In addition to children, the camp houses both males and females. In responding to interviews, the Malkohi camp manager states "The Malkohi camp is managed by NEMA and the State Emergency Management Agency (SEMA). NEMA at the federal level and SEMA at the state level."²⁶ Added to this," that the camp has been open for seven years and that its main goal is to give IDPs safety, food, medical care,

¹⁹ Commission on Human Security. *Human Security Now*. New York: United Nations (2003)

²⁰ United Nations Development Programme. *Human Development Report*. New York: Oxford University Press, (1994): p. 22-23

²¹ Francis M. Deng. *Human Security and the Global Challenge of Internal Displacement*. [Retrieved from <https://www.google.com/amp/s/www.brookings.edu/on-the-record/human-security-and-the-global-challenge-of-internal-displacement/amp/>] (2020): p.1-5 [Accessed February 20, 2023]

²² *Ibid* p.1

²³ Justina Amina Bitiyong Zemo et al. The plight of internally displaced persons in unofficial camps in the Federal capital territory of Nigeria, Abuja. *Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research*, Volume 2, Issue: (2019): p. 28-37

²⁴ International Organization for Migration (IOM) *Displacement tracking matrix—Nigeria* [Retrieved from <https://displacement.iom.int/nigeria>] (2022) (Accessed July 31, 2022)

²⁵ W. Ekezie. *An investigation of the essential health services available to the internally displaced population (IDPs) in Northern Nigeria*. University of Nottingham (2019)

²⁶ Interview with Malkohi camp manager

education, etc.”²⁷.He further states;” the camp first operated temporarily for only six months. In Adamawa, 10238 IDPs are living in four camps. There are 1238 internally displaced people (IDPs) in the Malkohi camp in Nigeria's Adamawa State.”²⁸

The Needs of IDPs: Women and Children

The ability to meet one's basic needs, such as those for food, clothing, health care, housing, and other material items, will improve the conditions of IDPs, particularly the needs of women and children. This section examines the basic needs of IDPs especially those of women and children. In an interview with IDPs inside the camp, the IDPs said” having our needs made in the camp, seems barely difficult, what we get as aid is what we lived on.”²⁹ To assess the needs of IDPs, particularly the needs of women and children. This section examined some of the health and food needs of IDPs, particularly the needs of women and children. This section investigated the experiences of IDPs through semi-structured interviews the problems that IDPs faced at the camp and the areas where further assistance is needed. In an interview with an internally displaced woman (IDW) inside the camp, the IDW said it was very hard to get used to life in the camp, and the ability of the authorities to help is a cause for concern;

“There have been several difficulties in adjusting to life in the camp. These include challenges with housing, finances, education, food, and other necessities. But issues with food, health, and safety are the major impediments to adjusting to life in this camp.”³⁰

Another added;

“There is no adequate feeding in the camp; we are congested in an unventilated structure, pointing to the accommodation. You can see our accommodation.”³¹

While one IDW stated;

“It is often hard for IDPs to use their basic rights to food and other household supplies for their homes.”³²

IDPs commented further on the state of the camps.

“ We lack access to medical facilities, we are vulnerable to all types of communicable diseases, and lack clean water.”³³

In responding to an interview question, one IDW added:

“The camp has a steady supply of food and other necessities like medical care, but the supply went down later.”

In response to these problems, the people in charge of the camp made sure we had food and other supplies twice a month. And for women and children, checkups every month.”³⁴ Having responded to interviews question about all the problems they were having in the camp, the displaced persons pleaded with the agencies concerned to help them more. To better understand the needs of IDPs particularly those of women and children, this paper discusses the health and food needs of IDPs.

Primarily, when it comes to health care, women and children have the most urgent needs, but most of the time, the government doesn't do enough to meet those needs. Women and children are particularly vulnerable when it

²⁷ Interview with Malkohi camp manager

²⁸ Interview with Malkohi camp manager

²⁹ IDPs in Malkohi Camp

³⁰ Female respondents, aged: 28

³¹ Female respondents, aged: 45

³² Male respondents, aged: 39

³³ Interviewed IDPs from the Malkohi camp

³⁴ Female respondents, aged:32

comes to health care. This is supported by evidence from Olusola Oladeji's³⁵ research, which corroborates our findings. The problem is that there is always a high risk of becoming pregnant during an emergency, but the response teams do not do enough to protect the women who are housed in these IDP camps and to keep a handle on the number of pregnant women. Since this is the case, the number of unplanned pregnancies keeps going up, even though it seems impossible to get an abortion in IDP camps.

Equally, Oluwakemi C. Amodu ³⁶ "60% of preventable maternal deaths, 53% of deaths under the age of five, and 45% of neonatal deaths happen in settings of conflict and displacement," says the World Health Organization. But the above numbers should be enough to convince both the government and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) that they need to pay special attention to the women and children living in IDP camps. Mental health problems, like post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), can also affect women and children. There's a chance that they were attacked or hurt in other ways before they got to the camp. Because poor mental health can result in death, IDP camps should consider mental health care and the treatment of psychological trauma. This is because of the connection between the two. Children and women living in IDP camps currently face several challenges, all of which could be alleviated if action were taken in response to the terrorist group. As a result of this, there would be no need for IDP camps.

Furthermore, every IDP who has been forced to leave their home because of an armed uprising or armed conflict has a hard time getting enough food. Children who have been displaced can suffer from malnutrition as a result of this. Throughout the entirety of the crisis, women and children have faced persistent challenges regarding securing adequate food supplies. The report from the World Food Programme makes this point abundantly clear for the states of Borno, Yobe, and Adamawa, located in the northeast. Millions of people in Nigeria are having their lives and ways of making a living disrupted as a result of the conflict. There are currently 4.4 million people in the northeast of Nigeria who are experiencing severe hunger, and there are 320,000 children who are suffering from severe malnutrition.³⁷

Government IDP Policy in Malkohi Camp

This section investigates Government IDP Policy in Malkohi and how IDP needs are being met by the government and aid organizations. The camp Manager commented; "As a government organization, NEMA assumes full accountability for running the camp."³⁸ Added to this;" according to NEMA Act 12 of 1999, as amended by Act 50 of 1999, my job is to get financial and technical help for Nigeria's disaster management from international organizations and non-governmental organizations (NGOs).;³⁹ collecting emergency relief supplies from local and foreign sources and international agencies and NGOs;⁴⁰ ensuring the effective distribution of emergency relief materials to victims of

³⁵Olusola Oladeji, B. O. Sexual Violence–Related Pregnancy Among Internally Displaced Women in an Internally Displaced Persons Camp in Northeast Nigeria. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*. [Retrieved January 23rd, 2023, <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/0886260518792252>.] (2018)

³⁶ C. Oluwafemi, M. S. Amodu. A Scoping Review of the Health of Conflict-Induced Internally Displaced Women in Africa. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* [Retrieved from Doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17041280>] ((2020, February 17)

³⁷ WFP: North-eastern Nigeria Emergency, <https://www.wfp.org/emergencies/nigeria-emergency> [Accepted January 23rd, 2023]

³⁸ Interview with Malkohi camp manager

³⁹ Federal Republic of Nigeria, National Emergency Management Agency Acts.1999. Section 6 (1)(h)

⁴⁰ Ibid., Section 6(1)(h)

natural or other disasters, and assisting in the rehabilitation of the victims where necessary.⁴¹ The camp manager further commented; “the federal government helps IDPs and is helped by NGOs like IOM, Nigeria Red Cross, RCRC, Cariters' Chat Voice, Faith-Based Organizations (FBOs), and others. NGOs help IDPs in the camp in a big way because they are the main contributors who give them food, shelter, and other necessities.”⁴² Finally, the manager confirmed that; “NGOs visit the camp to provide supplies for IDPs. Staff from NEMA and the FCT Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) occasionally visit the camp to offer assistance. They serve as the link between the populace, NGOs, and the government. Because we have heard of explosions and bombings of IDPs in other places, it is customary that before relief goods are brought to IDPs here, both the relief materials and donors are checked by NEMA or FEMA.”⁴³ The NEMA employee states, some of the significant challenges that have come up when trying to assist IDPs with their needs and problems. He explained the ways to consult with the camp residents about their needs and problems. And some of the problems that come up when trying to help displaced persons get back into their old or new communities NEMA officer commented;

“The government's funds are insufficient to support IDPs, so I speak with their representatives to learn more about their challenges and needs. It is challenging to reintegrate IDPs into the original community because of insecurity issues.”⁴⁴ NEMA officer suggested;

“To ensure the security of IDPs, the government must first work to eradicate terrorism before considering resettlement initiatives.”⁴⁵

Comparing Malkohi Camp with Other IDP Camps in Nigeria

It is important to compare the experiences of Women and Children in Malkohi camp to other camps in Nigeria to come to a more complete conclusion that shows the problems that IDPs face in general, not just in Malkohi camp. The paper analysis how well has government policies been able to meet the needs of IDPs, particularly the needs of women and children. Children are more susceptible to viral illnesses like water-borne illnesses and respiratory tract infections because they have less access to safe areas, food, water, health care, and education.⁴⁶ COOPI- Cooperazione Internazionale.⁴⁷ revealed the speed at which diseases like cholera and other illnesses spread through the community due to poor health and sanitation. This is supported by evidence from Moise C. Ngwa et al.⁴⁸ In August 2017, a cholera outbreak started in the Muna Garage IDPs camp in Borno State Nigeria. By October, it appeared in six local government areas with a total of 5,340 cases reported including 61 deaths. This outbreak was a result of the condition

⁴¹ Ibid., Section 6(1)(h)

⁴² Interview with Malkohi camp manager

⁴³ Interview with Yola Camp Manager, Malkohi Camp.

⁴⁴ Interview with a NEMA official in Yola, March 13, 2022

⁴⁵ Interview with a NEMA official in Yola, March 13, 2022

⁴⁶ O. Oluwabunmi, Niyi-Gafar, O.S Adelakun. The impact of viral diseases on the rights of vulnerable populations: COVID-19 and the Nigerian internally displaced child Social Sciences & Humanities Open, 6(1), 100268. [Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2022.100268>] (2022)

⁴⁷ COOPI, Cooperazione International. Multi-Sector Rapid Needs Assessment (MSNA) in Benisheikh and Ngamdu (Kaga LGA, Borno State)—November 2016. http://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/coopi_msna_kaga_lga.pdf (Accessed January 21, 2023.)

⁴⁸ C.Moise. Ngwa, Alemu Wondimagegnehu, et al. Cholera in Internally Displaced Person Camps in Borno State, 2017: A qualitative study of the multi-sectorial emergency response to stop the spread of the outbreak. Doi [Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1101/599787>.] (2019)

in the IDP camp like overflowing latrines, overcrowding, and open defecation were highly favorable to cholera transmission.

Atanda's⁴⁹ study shows that most IDPs who live outside of camps do so with host communities, in places of worship like churches and mosques, or inhumanly inhabitable buildings. "We do not have enough food to eat here in the camp; we are always hungry because, in the past two months, the people who work for the government have not brought us food," an IDP from Bakassi camp, which is the highest camp in Borno state, said.⁵⁰ Mary's⁵¹ research examines some of the problems in IDP camps, such as unemployment, poverty, hunger, a lack of electricity, and a lack of safety. These problems are found in Malkohi village, Rounde Killa village, Damare village, Kawan Wapa St. Theresa camp, and NYSC camp. "Women and children living in IDP camps lack access to necessities such as food. There are also insufficient medical facilities for these women, who frequently become pregnant as a result of their exploration and contracts numerous diseases."⁵² Olanike Adedokun,⁵³ investigated some camps in Nigeria. To access the health and nutrition of IDPs in camp. In Daudu Camp 1 and Camp 2, there were no designated health facilities on the camp premises but the health needs of IDPs were directly attended to by the well-equipped community clinic. IDPs had positive comments about the quality of services they received at the community health centers. Children and adults were well attended to with their health needs promptly catered for. Though the camp had records of maternity mortality, it was not associated with medical negligence because there was adequate care for children and pregnant women. In the Maraban Kajuru camp, there were three health workers, effective in attending to IDPs that require medical attention. However, there were inadequate mosquito nets for IDPs, and this made cases of malaria at a high rate. Also, a lot of children were malnourished because the camp could only provide meals to the IDPs once a day in the form of lunch. The IDPs thus had to feed themselves in the morning and at night.

This evidence from studies of other IDP camps indicates that the challenges faced by IDPs in the Malkohi camp are not unique but rather are experienced more generally. It also highlights some of the major gaps in government provision to meet the needs of IDPs, particularly the needs of women and children.

Conclusions

This paper examined the challenges faced by IDPs in adjusting to life in the Malkohi camp, which include coping with issues related to food, housing, health, safety, and other necessities. The paper examined how effective government policies have been able to meet the needs of IDPs, particularly the needs of women and children. Although IDPs in Malkohi camp faced challenges in adjusting to life in the camp, these have negatively affected their general well-being. While there are government policies that address the problems and needs of IDPs in the Malkohi camp, there are still gaps, particularly in addressing the needs of women and children. To this end, the Nigerian government's policy on camps as well as the distribution of aid to IDPs in the Malkohi does not lie only on protection and assisting IDPs but also to eradicate the challenges of IDPs in Nigeria. As such, aside from policies for the protection and assistance of

⁴⁹ Atanda S. Sambo. Internally Displaced Persons and Their Information Needs Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal) <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1512> (2017): p. 15–12. (As of November 12, 2021)

⁵⁰ Ibid.p.4

⁵¹ Mary Ann Ajayi. The Challenges of Human Security Among Displaced Women and Children in Northeast Nigeria [Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327671194>]. p.169_(2017)

⁵² Ibid. p.169

⁵³ Olanike Adedokun. Internally Displaced Children in Nigeria: A Rights-Based Situational Appraisal. In. Adeola, R.(eds)National Protection of Internally Displaced Persons in Africa. Sustainable Development Goals series. Springer, Cham. (Retrieved from https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-66884-6_72021).

IDPs, the Nigerian government policies provide preventive measures for addressing the challenges of IDPs in the Malkohi camp.

IDPs are secure by putting them in camps, as a major policy of the Nigerian government. Hence, HST's role in protecting the lives of IDPs includes providing policy guidelines for conceptualizing and creating plans for preventing displacement, guaranteeing safety and assistance during relocation, and exploring possibilities for long-term solutions. The Malkohi camp suggests that the Nigerian government's policies of housing IDPs and providing relief supplies every month or three months do not offer adequate solutions to the challenges faced by IDPs, especially for women and children. It takes a long time to get aid to IDPs. Moreso, displaced children can't get a regular education, the houses they are given are in bad shape, and they can't get medical care in the camp.

This paper contributes to the existing literature by addressing some of the gaps in existing studies. For example, the policies put in place to assist IDPs, how effective these policies assist women and children, and what problems IDPs face. It makes a significant contribution to a more systematic understanding of the challenges faced by IDPs in the Malkohi camp in Adamawa state, Nigeria as well as the effectiveness and efficacy of government policy responses in addressing these challenges. The policies' responses require more dedication from the government, organizations, and NGOs than its policy framework by instituting purposeful deriving objectives, that ensure IDPs are protected in the short term and have unlimited access to their basic requirements. The basic analysis of the implication co-occurrences that resulted from our investigation suggests a threat to the human security of IDPs. The fact that the policy responses of the Nigerian government do not offer adequate solutions to the challenges faced by IDPs -suggests that a specialized form of response, for example, health policy needs and social policy meant to be included in the larger government policies dimension. If this policy is incorporated it will provide a guide to address the specific needs of IDPs, which might provide the government, organizations, and agencies a new dimension to respond to the challenges of IDPs. Further research is required to develop a more comprehensive analysis of the preventive measures for addressing the challenges of IDPs in the Malkohi camp particularly the needs of women and children in the camp.

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References

- [1] Abidde, Sabella O. *The Challenges of Refugees and Internally Displaced Persons in Africa*. Switzerland Springer: (2021) p.3
- [2] Adamu, A. and Rasheed Z. H. *Prognosis and Diagnosis of the Effects of Insecurity on Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Northern Nigeria.* Global Journal of Human-Social Science: Political Science, 16(1), 2016: 10–21
- [3] Adelakun, Olanike. *Internally Displaced Children in Nigeria: A Rights-Based Situational Appraisal*. In. Adeola, R.(eds) *National Protection of Internally Displaced Persons in Africa*. Sustainable Development Goals series. Springer, Cham. (Retrieved from https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-66884-6_7(2021)).

- [4] Ajayi, Mary Ann. *The Challenges of Human Security Among Displaced Women and Children in Northeast Nigeria* [Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327671194>] (2017): p.169
- [5] Akuto, G.W. *Challenges of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Nigeria: Implications for Counselling and the Role of Key Stakeholders*. 5(2) 2017: p. 21–27. [Retrieved from <http://seahipaj.org/journals/ci/june2017/IJIPSD/full/IJIPSD-I-4-2017.pdf>]
- [6] Amaechi, Louisa N. *Human Security of Internationally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Terro-Counterterrorism and Communal Conflicts in Northcentral Nigeria*. Owerri: Federal University of Technology: 2019: p.24
- [7] Azam, J.P. *Betting on Displacement: Oil, Violence, and the Switch to Civilian Rule in Nigeria*. Brookings Institution (2005). The University of Bern Project on International Displacement: Addressing Internal Displacement: A Framework for National Responsibility. (2009)
- [8] Commission on Human Security. *Human Security Now*. New York: United Nations (2003)
- [9] COOPI, *Cooperazione International. Multi-Sector Rapid Needs Assessment (MSNA) in Benisheikh and Ngamdu (Kaga LGA, Borno State)—November 2016*. [Retrieved from http://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/coopi_msna_kaga_lga.pdf (Accessed January 21, 2023.)
- [10] Deng, Francis M. *Human Security and the Global Challenge of Internal Displacement*. [Retrieved from <https://www.google.com/amp/s/www.brookings.edu/on-the-record/human-security-and-the-global-challenge-of-internal-displacement/amp/>] 2020: p.1-5 [Accessed February 20, 2023]
- [11] Ekezie, W. *An investigation of the essential health services available to the internally displaced population (IDPs) in Northern Nigeria*. University of Nottingham (2019)
- [12] Eneanya, Augustine Nduka. *Handbook of Research on Environmental Policies for Emergency Management and Public Safety USA*: IGI Global, 2018: p. 110
- [13] The Federal Republic of Nigeria, National Emergency Management Agency Acts.1999. Section 6 (1)(h)
- [14] Funmi, F. *Coping with Challenges of the Internally Displaced Person* Feature Slider [Retrieved from <http://dailyindependentnigeria.com/2014/07/coping-with-challenges-of-internally-displaced-persons-features-slider/>] (2014) [Accessed on October 12, 2022]
- [15] International Organization for Migration (IOM) Displacement tracking matrix—Nigeria [Retrieved from <https://displacement.iom.int/nigeria>] (2022) (Accessed July 31, 2022)
- [16] Kuwali, Dan. *From Durable Solutions to Holistic Solutions: Displacement Prevention in Africa*. African Journal of Legal Studies 6, South Africa: Martinus Nijhoff Publishers: (2013) p. 265-285
- [17] Ladan, M. T. *Migration, Trafficking, Human Rights, and Refugees under International Law: A Case Study of Africa Nigeria*: Ahmadu Bello University Press. (2006)
- [18] Mba, Ruth. *IDPs and the Need for Reinterpretation* (Retrieved from [https://www.medium.com/@ruthmba/the-plight-of-internally-displaced-persons-idps-and-the-need-for-reinterpretation-B7555c212f37\(2017\)](https://www.medium.com/@ruthmba/the-plight-of-internally-displaced-persons-idps-and-the-need-for-reinterpretation-B7555c212f37(2017))) [As of November 15, 2021]
- [19] Moise C. Ngwa, Wondimagegnehu Alemu, et al. *Cholera in Internally Displaced Person Camps in Borno State, 2017: A qualitative study of the multi-sectorial emergency response to stop the spread of the outbreak*. Doi [Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1101/599787>.] (2019)
- [20] National policy on internally displaced persons (IDPs) in Nigeria, Federal Republic of Nigeria, August 2012: p.11
- [21] Oladeji, Olusola, B. O. *Sexual Violence–Related Pregnancy Among Internally Displaced Women in an Internally Displaced Persons Camp in Northeast Nigeria*. Journal of Interpersonal Violence. [Retrieved January 23rd, 2023, <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/0886260518792252>.] (2018)
- [22] Olanrewaju, Faith Osasumwen, Omotoso Femi, and Alabi Joshua Olaniyi. *Datasets on the challenges of forced displacement and coping strategies among displaced women in selected IDP camps in Nigeria* [Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6091441/>] (2018). [As of October 27, 2021]

- [23] Oluwabunmi O, Gafar Niyi-, Adelokun O.S. *The impact of viral diseases on the rights of vulnerable populations: COVID-19 and the Nigerian internally displaced child* Social Sciences & Humanities Open, 6(1), 100268. [Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2022.100268>] (2022)
- [24] Oluwafemi, C., Amodu M. S. *A Scoping Review of the Health of Conflict-Induced Internally Displaced Women in Africa*. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health) [Retrieved from Doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17041280>] ((2020, February 17)
- [25] Raji, Shittu, Adekayaojas Folashade Arinola, et al. *North-Eastern Nigeria: Assessing the National Emergency Management Agency's Response Capacity to the Plights of Internally Displaced Persons*. [Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/352277395_Northeastern_Nigeria_assessing_the_response_capacity_of_the_National_Emergency_Management_Agency_to_the_plights_of_internally_displaced_persons] 2021: p. 2–3. [Accessed November 11, 2021]
- [26] Rubia, M., I. Marcos, P.A Muening. *Increased risk of heart disease among foreign-born females residing in the United States America* Journal Preventive of Medicine (2002) 222:30-5
- [27] Sambo, Atanda S. *Internally Displaced Persons and Their Information Needs* Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal) <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1512> (2017): p. 15–12. (As of November 12, 2021)
- [28] Shimawua, Dominic. *Appraisal of the Management of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Nigeria* International Journal of Knowledge and Dynamic Systems, volume 14, number 2: 2020: p. 65–70
- [29] Tadjbakhsh, Shahrbanou. *Routledge Handbook of Human Security: In Defense of the Broad View of Human Security*. (2013). p. 43 [As of November 22, 2021]
- [30] UNCHR. *Nigeria Situation*. Retrieved from *Situation Nigeria Situation* (UNHCR.org) (2023) [Accessed March 18, 2023].
- [31] United Nations Development Programme. *Human Development Report*. New York: Oxford University Press 1994: p. 22–23
- [32] WFP: North-eastern Nigeria Emergency, <https://www.wfp.org/emergencies/nigeria-emergency> [Accepted January 23rd, 2023]
- [33] Zemo, Justina Amina Bitiyong et al. *The plight of internally displaced persons in unofficial camps in the Federal capital territory of Nigeria, Abuja*. Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research, Volume 2, Issue: 2019: p. 28–37

Mrs. Miriam Augustine Sambo

